

**NIGERIAN SORGHUM PRODUCTION - PAST, PRESENT
AND FUTURE POSSIBILITIES.**

By

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Abstract

This report is a survey of sorghum production in Nigeria. Sorghum is one of the upland cereal crops grown widely in the country. With regard to national spread, it is the foremost of cultivated crops under Nigerian agriculture. It is a source of a variety of food menu for the people of Nigeria, meeting the nutritional needs of children as well as the adults. The survey discovered that, the relevance of the crop is on the decline, partly due to stiff competition from both maize and millet. Coupled with this is the fact that, the percentage of able-bodied men that are engaged in crop farming is reducing very fast compared with the growing population. However, enrolment of undergraduates in Agriculture appears to be an encouragement that can fill the gap being created by the ageing and dying illiterate and peasant farmers. The attempts of successive Governments to boost food production, including sorghum are recognized in the paper. The need to bring back the lost glory of sorghum production is emphasized and recommendations are made to achieve this laudable drive.

Introduction

Sorghum that is locally called guinea corn, is a member of the great grass family called *Poaceae*, sub-family *panicoideae* and the tribe *andropogoneae*. It belongs to the group of domesticated crops known as cereals. Cereal is defined as a grass grown for its small, edible grain and the most important source of world food over the ages, (Onwueme and Sinha; 1991). The crop is the fifth most important world cereal, taking its position after wheat, rice, maize and barley, (Onwueme and Sinha, 1991;

Martin *et al*, 1976; Doggett, 1988; FAO, 1986). This central or significant position of Sorghum among the cereals is equally the case among all the world cultivated crops. Guinea corn is very significant both as a food crop for man and feed for his livestock. In advanced economy of the world, the bulk of the grains produced is used as livestock feed beside the use of the crop as forage. However in African countries, over eighty percent (80%) of the total output is used for human food unlike in the U.S.A. where only 20-25 percent is directly consumed by the populace; (Doggett, 1988, Onwueme and Sihan, 1991). In Nigeria, while the grains are consumed in various forms; the dry leaves left after grain harvest serve as hay for ruminant animals especially cattle and goats.

Generally, the concern of man to increase food production is not just a recent development. Since the prediction of Malthus (1798), the fear of hunger predominating the affairs of man has been on focus locally, nationally, continentally and globally. Nations have risen up to promote, encourage and get involved in the expanded programme of food production. Successive Governments in Nigeria had embarked on grass root programmes aimed at revolutionizing agricultural production. Such programmes include National Accelerated Food Production Programme (NAFFP); Operation Feed the Nation (OFN), Green Revolution (GR); Directorate of Food and Rural Infrastructure (DIFRI). All these were efforts on the part of the Federal Government of Nigeria to save Nigerians from hunger and starvation.

Four (4) grain crops have been in the fore front among all the crops in Nigeria. These are maize, guinea corn, millet and rice. In the past, Sorghum was the foremost grain crop in Nigeria as a result of the following factors:

- Its long association with the rural farmers.
- The availability of different varieties adapted to different environmental conditions.
- Its importance in the diets of the people.
- Easy post-harvest handling or processing.
- Longer storage life, unlike root and tuber crops.

In addition, the varied nature of sorghum with different varieties also result in wide differences in yield. For instance, in Borno State; the yield can be as low as 575kg/ha, while it may be as high as 1,140.0kg/ha in Kaduna State (Agboola, 1979). In the wetter guinea savanna of Kwara State, the yields of the tall varieties of guinea corn can be as high as 1,820-2,018kg/ha, (Ajiboye, 2010). These wide variations

confirm the general belief that, the yields of many Nigerian crops are very low in comparison with their potentials; (Olayide *et al*, 1972, Agboola, Federal office of statistics, 2001). To realize the expected potentials, the following requirements were advocated:

- * Improvement in crop structure through cultural practice and more importantly breeding efforts.
- * Re-organization of production efforts.
- * Coordinated input utilization especially appropriate fertilizers.
- * Control of pests and diseases at critical phenological state.
- * Adoption of crop varieties for different ecological zones.
- * Adoption of optimal sowing density as a product of sowing rate and spacing.

Sorghum grains are processed into various forms of food in Nigeria. It can be consumed as cooked whole grains, especially with cowpea popularly called beans by market retailers. Beside, the grains can be soaked in water for about 72 hours, followed by milling or grinding. Sieving may or may not be done. Water is added, stirred vigorously and left for hours, preferably over night. The product is locally called "ogi". This can be prepared into "akamun" that is a famous breakfast menu usually taken with "moin-moin" or "akara" by millions of Nigerians. The "ogi" can also be made into a paste for the preparation of yam or cassava flour into "amala" that is another famous lunch or dinner for multitudes of Nigerians. The preparation of "ogi" paste for cassava flour usually prevents the stomach disorders that some people experience when the cassava flour "laafun" is taken solely. Then the preparation of sorghum whole grains into "tuwo-dawa" in some cultures in Nigeria along with other patterns of consumption make sorghum a popular food crop in Nigeria. The grains also serve as raw materials for a number of beverage industries.

Nigerian Sorghum Production Past Performance

Nigeria has over the years been an agricultural county. She is well endowed with favourable climatic and soil conditions that allow massive production of many food crops. The fact of environmental variation noticeable in the country demands that, different ecological zones specialize in different crops that biologically coincide with the natural vegetation. Consequently, while the wetter South is well disposed to tree crops, roots and tubers, the North that has the vegetal cover of grasses carries such shallow feeding crops as cereals and grain legumes. The significance of any crop is determined in terms of its (i) annual output (ii) average yield per hectare, (iii) land area covered (iv) geographical spread. In terms of these yardsticks, sorghum in

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the past ranked first among all the crops grown in Nigeria, (Annual Abstract of Statistics 1996, 1998, 2001). There were places in the country where over 50%, 30-49% and 10-20% of the arable land were planted with sorghum, (UNAP/FAO 1969, Olayide 1976, Agboola, 1979). While the middle belt States of Kwara, Kogi, Benue, Nassarawa and Plateau accounted for only 7% of the total guinea corn output in Nigeria, the core northern States of Kebbi, Niger, Kaduna, Bauchi, Taraba, Yobe, Adamawa, Gombe, Katsina, Sokoto, Kano and Jigawa accounted for 92% of Nigerian guinea corn output.

However, the land areas devoted to sorghum as well as the global output have been on the decline in the last three decades. The Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) report of 1986 indicates sorghum production of 65 million tonnes on 47 million hectares, while that of 2002 shows 42 million hectares and 55 million tonnes. Onwueme and Sinha (1991), had observed that, sorghum is now being substituted by maize in many parts of tropical Africa. Coincidentally too, in Nigeria, the sorghum crop is losing prominence when compared with maize, (Federal Office of Statistics 1995, 1996, 1998, 2001). There is a keen competition between maize and guinea corn for recognition and acceptability. It appears that maize is having a steady edge over sorghum. Among other reasons adduced by Onwueme and Sinha for this gradual subjugation of sorghum by maize is the fact that maize gives higher yield per unit area.

Table-1 clearly indicates the declining fortune of sorghum production in Nigeria. In the most recent years; the average yield/ha of sorghum has a marginal increase over that of earlier years. This notwithstanding, the land area cropped by sorghum has been declining and so is the total national output. This fall in the general output of guinea corn is in consonance with the report of Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) of the United Nations as well as the position of Onwueme and Sinha. With the national population on the increase, the trend in sorghum production should be a major concern to the stakeholders in agronomy, plant-breeding, crop physiology and crop protection.

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TABLE I. ESTIMATED LAND AREA, OUTPUT AND YIELD PER HECTARE OF SORGHUM IN NIGERIA OVER A DECADE

CROPPING SEASON	ESTIMATED LAND AREA IN '000HECTARES	ESTIMATED OUTPUT IN '000 METRIC TONNES	ESTIMATED YIELD PER HECTARE (KG)
1995/1996	5,896	7,608	1,155
1996/1997	5,803	7,959	1,080
1997/1998	5,910	8,430	1,426
1998/1999	5,870	7,066	1,204
1999/2000	5,861	6,885	1,175
2000/2001	n.a	n.a	n.a
2001/2002	n.a	n.a	n.a
2002/2003	n.a	n.a	n.a
2003/2004	3,952.81	4,653.1	1,177.2
2004/2005	3,956.71	4,545.3	1,148.8
2005/2006	4,597.56	5,739.2	1,248.3
2006/2007	4,578.00	6,474.0	1,414.0
2007/2008	4,113.68	5,218.4	1,269.0

n.a = Not available.

Source: Federal Office of Statistics (2001).

National Bureau of Statistics (2009).

It must be borne in mind that, guinea corn dishes such as "*tuwo-ndawa*" among the people of Northern Nigeria, various "*ogi*" menu for weaning children and "*akamun*" for adults across regional boundaries of Nigeria are cultural foods of the people such that, guinea corn must be seen as a major food crop whose production must be enhanced at all cost. Foreign foods that are made from other cereals like oats, barley and wheat cannot be substituted for those made from local cereals at least for economic and political reasons. As part of efforts to promote grain production, the Federal Government of Nigeria once established the National Grains production Company (NGPC) and the Nigerian Grains Board (NGB) as parastatals in the Federal Ministry of Agriculture.

Presently, there are no known commercial grain production farms in Nigeria. What is regarded as the national output is from the collective efforts of peasant and ageing farmers whose population is not a match with the total head count in Nigeria

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that is being estimated to be over 150 millions. Table-2 shows the employment in crop farming in Nigeria according to the National Bureau of Statistics, 2009.

TABLE 2. MALE EMPLOYMENT IN CROPFARMING

CROPPING SEASON	MALE EMPLOYMENT
1999/2000	29,763,000
2000/2001	27,765,000
2001/2002	27,173,000
2002/2003	29,310,000
2003/2004	n.a
2004/2005	29,413,000
2005/2006	28,435,000
2006/2007	n.a
2007/2008	n.a

n.a = not available.

Source: National Bureau of Statistics, 2009.

NIGERIAN SORGHUM PRODUCTION PRESENT PERFORMANCE

Report from the Food and Agriculture organization (FAO) has indicated that, sorghum production is very much on the decline. Presently too in Nigeria, production is on the decline. Comparing the four (4) prominent cereal crops grown in Nigeria; sorghum is under a serious threat not only from maize but also from millet (Table 3).

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**TABLE 3: ESTIMATED OUTPUT OF CEREAL CROPS IN NIGERIA
(’000 METRIC TONNES).**

CROPPING SEASON	MAIZE	SORGHUM	MILLET	RICE
2000/2001	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a
2001/2002	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a
2002/2003	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a
2003/2004	5,190.94	4,653.1	4,232.77	2,980.57
2004/2005	5,498.89	4,545.3	4,226.78	3,183.39
2005/2006	6,394.78	5,739.2	5,273.05	3,247.52
2006/2007	7,023.0	6,474.0	5,940.0	3,333.0
2007/2008	9,113.71	5,218.4	4,367.8	3,369.7

n.a = not available

Source: National Bureau of Statistics, 2009.

The present dwindling status of sorghum is a challenge to all stakeholders as to how to open up new frontiers for guinea corn to boost its output. Agbede *et al* (2008), observed that, the increasing demand for sorghum both for food and industrial raw materials is calling for the extension of the crop beyond its natural enclave of the savanna into the forest-savanna transition zone of Nigeria. Similarly, Harris *et al* (2007), emphasized that sorghum is an important source of food, feed and biofuel especially in the semi-arid tropics of the world and hence the need to promote its production.

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Oguntola (2007), observed that, there is a global climate change and this change is most profound or agriculture. Analyses indicate that, higher temperatures are expected in the coming years. Drought problem will become more rampant especially in lower latitudes where the most of the world's poorest people live. According to this observer, a 40% decline in agricultural productivity is predicted by the 2,080^s as recorded heat waves continue to affect the wheat growing regions of the world. Many will be at the brink of chronic hunger especially in Africa. An

agricultural down turn of 30% has been predicted and such will force farmers to abandon traditional crops in favour of more heat-resistant or tolerant ones. Maize according to Oguntola, is a crop that a change in climate will affect adversely in the growing regions with a potential 20% drop in production over the next 25 years. It was concluded that, crops that can serve as an economic bridge in hard times are needed. Maunder (2002), classified sorghum as the global grain crop of the future as a result of certain peculiar features of the crop. According to Maunder, sorghum tolerates drought, soil toxicities and temperature extremes more effectively than other cereals.

Furthermore, some investigators have also projected that, decreased precipitation is expected with global warming coupled with drier regimes throughout the tropical world, (Kellogg and Zhao, 1958; Manabe and Wetherald, 1986; Rind *et al.*, 1990). Of all the tropical cereals, sorghum is the most favoured under the reality of this climate change, Kimball, (1983). The general tolerance of sorghum to harsh, drought-prone environments was also reported by Harris *et al.* (2007); Mullet *et al.* (2001), Sanchez *et al.* (2002) and Edwards *et al.* (2004). The basis for the tolerance of sorghum to environmental stress includes the following:-

- Low transpiration rate because of relatively small leaf area, (Onwueme and Sinha, 1991).
- Dense and deep-reaching root system, (Martin, *et al.* 1976; Sigmand and Gustar, 1991, Anon, 1975).
- Ability to stop all growth and metabolism in times of severe dryness, (Sigmund and Gustar, 1991; Onwueme and Sinha 1991).
- The lamina rolls up under stress which reduces leaf surface area exposed to sun; thereby minimizing evapotranspiration, Cabley (1976).
- The leaves and stems are covered by a waxy material that reduces moisture loss, Onwueme and Sinha, (1991).

Consequently, the global trend and the future projection of sorghum as the Global Grain Crop of the Future (GGCF) demand that, a new perspective for sorghum has to be developed. Existing reports (Ajiboye, 2010) now confirm that sorghum frontiers can be profitably extended beyond the dry savanna of Northern Nigeria. The red, white and cream seeded varieties of the tall sorghum type are very promising in the wetter guinea savanna of Kwara State with the yield range of 1,820-2,018kg/ha under optional sowing density. Indeed the much wetter South-West States where maize is produced should also be explored for sorghum production, Agbede *et al.* (2008).

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While it is a fact that, the male employment in crop farming in Nigeria does not appear to correlate with the growing Nigerian population (see Table 2); the shortfall can as well be bridged by ever increasing graduates of Agriculture (Table 4).

TABLE 4: TOTAL ENROLMENT INTO AGRICULTURE BY UNDERGRADUATES IN NIGERIAN UNIVERSITIES.

SESSION	TOTAL ENROLMENT
1993/1994	15,428
1994/1995	12,765
1995/1996	18,605
1996/1997	20,340
1997/1998	21,251
1998-2002	n.a (not available)
2002/2003	27,201
2003/2004	30,457
2004/2005	26,455
2005/2006	22,022
2006/2007	22,604

Sources:-

Annual Abstract of Statistics, 2001

Annual Abstract of Statistics, 2009

Beside University graduates, there are other thousands that studied Agricultural Education in over seventy Colleges of Education across Nigeria. The curriculum nowadays is so designed to professionalize agriculture. The University degree used to be B.Sc Agriculture. This has generally given way to B. Agric degree. The orientation is such that will make graduates of Agriculture self-employed as well as become employers of labour. As graduates of Medicine, Law, Engineering can go into actual practice, even so can those that graduated in Agriculture. In the Colleges of Education; Vocational Agriculture is the emphasis so that, NCE graduates can go

into actual practice after leaving the College. Feedbacks from NCE graduates on the field are confirming this expectation more so under the unpleasant reality of gross graduate unemployment. In the years gone by, there used to be farm settlement scheme especially in the South-West of Nigeria. The reality of our time demands that, such laudable and promising schemes be brought back. Right now, some States in Nigeria are talking of such agricultural-based programmes as Agricultural Master Plan (AMP), Agricultural Transformation Agenda (ATA). These programmes are aimed at making the states the Agricultural hub of Nigeria and even West Africa. However, if the saying that "if you go about on a scheme the same way you have always done; you will surely get the results that you always got" is not to be roundly established; there must be a new approach to the execution of agricultural plans in Nigeria. There must be the grassroot mobilization of trained, equipped and willing graduates of agriculture in such plans. This is the cornerstone of the performance possibilities of Nigerian sorghum production. With the general perception for an enhanced sorghum production in an environment in which the crop will thrive; the factors that will contribute to the achievement of the goal have to be put in place. With the farms and rural areas virtually deserted by able-bodied people; the time is ripe to re-classify farming as an occupation for the literates and the enlightened. The greatest problem of peasant farmers is lack of access to capital for their farming operations. The so called agricultural loans earmarked by the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) and the commercial banks hardly get to the actual primary producers. The Nigerian elites and political lords intercept the loans for different investments other than anything that has to do with agriculture. No wonder then, virgin lands abound in Nigeria between this human settlement and another waiting to be cleared for cropping purposes. Introduction of Graduate Agricultural Loan Scheme (GALS) can be embarked upon especially by the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN). The loan which is expected to be interest-free should be such that re-payment cannot start until after five (5) years. This duration will allow the beneficiaries to really get established with the farm projects becoming self-sustaining and self-financing. After this time lag; re-payment will be easy and the farm business will still be thriving. It is practically impossible for one to invest a loan in farming and get established with re-payment schedule starting a year or two later. Risks, uncertainties, failures and disappointments characterize agricultural enterprises, thus allowances have to be given to all these for young graduates to mobilize courage and confidence enough to embark on crop production. This is what Nigeria needs if sorghum production will be enhanced and made to attain its potentials among other cereal crops.

CONCLUSION

For several decades in the past, it was observed that between 70-75 percent of the Nigerian populace were engaged on the farm, Olayide (1976). The production of staple food crops was high, Nigeria was an exporter of a number of farm produce, the national currency was strong and the economy was vibrant. This golden era is gone; food production has nose-dived to a miserable extent. Only about an estimated 30 millions of the male population are employed in crop farming (see Table 2) to feed an estimated population of about 150 million Nigerians. This translates to about 20 percent unlike the past 70-75 percent engaged in crop farming. Sorghum production is declining both in land area under the crop as well as the total output despite the fact that, the national population is on the increase. Yet, of all the cereal crops grown in Nigeria, sorghum is the most tolerant to environmental stress and it has been described as the global grain crop of the future in this regard and for the present reality of global climate change. The crop has been much confined to the savanna area of the North thus, limiting the hectarage and the national output. Findings now show that, sorghum can be raised in the guinea savanna as well as in forest/savanna zone of Nigeria where upland cereals like maize are produced, (Agbede *et al* (2008); Ajiboye, (2010). Obviously, more capable hands are required to promote sorghum production in Nigeria. Thousands of agricultural graduates are on ground in Nigeria that can be mobilized by the Federal Government in the programme of accelerated sorghum production.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- * The old dream and drive for National Grains production Company and the Nigerian Grains Board should be revived with a new national zeal.
- * The Federal Government should go into partnership with each State Government to establish an expansive integrated grain farm project in which well trained agricultural graduates are employed to manage.
- * There is the need to introduce the Private Public partnership (PPP) initiative into sorghum production which will guarantee easier land acquisition for commercial production.
- * There is the challenge to the National Universities Commission (NUC) and National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE) to further strengthen the curriculum of agricultural programmes of Universities and

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- * Colleges to carry more convincing professional outlook.
- * Greater access to agricultural loan facilities from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) with more flexible terms that will encourage willing agricultural graduates to venture into commercial sorghum production.
- * Re-payment of bank loans should not start until after five (5) years of taking the loans. This will allow the beneficiaries of such loans to stabilize and break even before re-payment commences.
- * Deciduous forest zone and the guinea savanna of Nigeria should be opened up for massive sorghum production particularly, using the late maturing varieties of the tall type of sorghum.
- * The old farm settlements scheme of some Southern States of Nigeria should be resuscitated for the promotion of sorghum production drive.
- * The need for a new national awareness campaign for sorghum production is greatly advocated, especially at the approach of a cropping season.
- * Research activities especially on breeding efforts to produce more high yielding varieties should be intensified.
- * Provision of big storage silos across the country is central in the bid to promote the National Grain Reserve.
- * Encouragement of cooperative farming among trained professionals. The bank should however, have a Farm Project Monitoring Unit (FPMU) for such loans.

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